

EOSC-IF

EOSC Data Transfer: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines

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EOSC-IF / EOSC Data Transfer: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines

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Abstract

The EOSC Data Transfer service is allowing users to easily transfer datasets discoverable via the EOSC Portal to EOSC Compute facilities. The guidelines part of this document describe the API that provides the Data Transfer capability to the EOSC Portal as a generic, abstract Data Transfer Service. The document lists the standards used, links to related Interoperability guidelines used, and offers an example of service implementing the given guidelines.

Version History

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● Glossary

The EOSC Future project's Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JOCK>

1 Intended Audience

There are two intended audiences for this EOSC-Core Interoperability Guideline: (1) the developers and technical experts from organisations that developed and/or are operating a data transfer service, particularly those that would like their data transfer service to be integrated into the EOSC Portal, and (2) the data repository owners that want to integrate their repositories into the EOSC Data Transfer service by translating PIDs to records in their repositories into lists of source files ready to be transferred.

2 Description and main features

The EOSC Data Transfer is an EOSC Core horizontal service that is integrated with the EOSC Portal and enables easy transfer of datasets (e.g. for analysis) from data repositories - onboarded to the EOSC Marketplace - to computing infrastructure accessible to EOSC users.

Data transfers are the copying or movement of data from one storage system to another. Storage systems support transfer of data over one or more data transfer protocols. Data transfer services, particularly those that can do bulk data transfers of massive amounts of data, across heterogeneous storage systems, with advanced features such as retries, priorities, error checking and correction, policy based scheduling, etc. are very complex products. Implementation of such a product is out of scope for the EOSC Data Transfer service. And although there are many such data transfer services, each supporting transfers over multiple transfer protocols, there is no universal transfer service that supports transfers over all protocols. Nor is there one that (a) has a pluggable architecture that can be easily extended to support new transfer protocols, and (b) is available to EOSC users. The myriad of data transfer services available to EOSC users, each offers a different API, a different UI, support a different set of transfer protocols, sometimes even supporting just a subset of features depending on the transfer protocol used. Therefore, a solution is needed to wrap all these existing data transfer services with a generic interface.

The EOSC Data Transfer service makes it possible for owners/operators of data transfer services to offer their functionality to EOSC through a unified programmatic interface. It defines the operations (and the entities involved in those operations) of a generic data transfer service, acting as a wrapper over existing data services. By providing an abstract layer that could be implemented by data transfer providers, the EOSC Data Transfer ensures service composability and the openness of the EOSC Exchange.

The EOSC Data Transfer is comprised of two main components (see also [Section 4](#)): the GUI that is integrated with the EOSC Portal and the EOSC Data Transfer REST API that is implementing an abstract layer for data transfers, wrapping the available data transfer services in the EOSC Marketplace (e.g. EGI Data Transfer). Integrating your data transfer service or data repository with the EOSC Data Transfer service means integrating it with the EOSC Data Transfer REST API, while the GUI remains the same.

3 Response to Community Need

The EOSC Data Transfer provides a way to efficiently transfer datasets from repositories registered in EOSC to Compute nodes via a Web interface abstracting over multiple technologies to transfer data. Many implementations for transferring datasets are available, each tailored to specific storage solutions/protocols or ways of authentication.

Users can browse the EOSC Portal to find datasets, then initiate data transfers to the storage in an accessible computing infrastructure. In particular, the EOSC Data Transfer service facilitates 3 sets of functionalities:

- Parsing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)
- Creating and managing data transfers
- Managing storage elements

4 High-level Service Architecture

Figure 1 shows the high-level technical architecture of the EOSC Data Transfer service as part of the EOSC platform.

Figure 1 - High level architecture of the EOSC Data Transfer service

The following components are part of the architecture:

- The main component is the EOSC Data Transfer API that implements the operations and queries supported by the generic data transfer service, and provides the reference integration of one of the data transfer services available in EOSC.
- A new GUI component in EOSC Explore has been implemented that can invoke the EOSC Data Transfer API to perform transfers and management of storage elements. This GUI component will show up on the details page of those datasets in the EOSC Marketplace that can be parsed by a data repository parser integrated in the EOSC Data Transfer API.
- Authentication and authorization is based on the EOSC AAI, although the EOSC Data Transfer API does not require or use any authentication or authorization, it just forwards it to the data transfer service that gets selected to handle a specific operation. Some storage systems may use a different authentication/authorization than the transfer service that will perform the data transfers to that storage system. Thus, in order to authenticate to some storage servers and perform transfers and/or manage storage elements, separate credentials (e.g. S3 access/secret keys) may be needed.

5 Definitions

This table presents the terms/acronyms used in this document, together with their definition or explanation.

Table 1 - Definitions

Term	Definition
Data Transfer	An asynchronous, secure, and restartable exchange of data between two systems.
Storage Element	A storage element is where the user's data is stored. It is a generic term meant to hide the complexity of different types of storage technologies. It can mean both an element of the storage system's hierarchy (directory, folder, container, bucket, etc.) and the entity that stores the data (file, object, etc.).
Storage Type	A concept used by the Data Transfer API to select the transfer service to perform a task. It is a pair of a transfer protocol and an (optional) storage system instance.
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
PID	Persistent Identifiers are long-lasting references to a document, file, web page, or other object.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier is a specific type of PID that identifies an object, which can be physical, digital, or abstract.

6 Licensing Information

The EOSC Data Transfer API is licensed under Apache Licence 2.0¹

7 Related Guidelines

Table 2 presents the EOSC Interoperability guidelines related to the guideline being described as well as where compliance is recommended or required in order to interoperate:

Table 2 - Related Guidelines

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	relatedIdentifier
EOSC Interoperability Guideline	EOSC Interoperability Guideline for AAI	Interoperability Guidelines describe policies and best practices for AAI-facilitated interoperability	Pending formal publication

¹ <https://github.com/EGI-Federation/eosc-future-data-transfer/blob/main/LICENSE>

8 Adopted Standards

Table 3 provides a description of the main standards, protocols, APIs, etc. adopted by this Interoperability Guideline, and that are exposed to the external world. This table includes standards that would influence the manner in which a Provider would interoperate with or integrate the service, and lists them together with authoritative references.

Table 3 - Adopted Standards

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	related Identifier
Protocol	REST API	RESTful APIs are API that conform to the design principles of the REST, or <i>representational state transfer</i> architectural style.	
Standard	OIDC standard	OpenID Connect (OIDC) is an identity layer built on top of the OAuth 2.0 framework. It allows third-party applications to verify the identity of the end-user and to obtain basic user profile information. OIDC uses JSON web tokens (JWTs), which can be obtained using flows conforming to the OAuth 2.0 specification.	
Protocol	S3 API	The S3 API provides the capability to list, store, retrieve, and delete objects (or binary files) in AWS S3 or any compatible Object Storage system.	
Protocol	WebDAV	Web Distributed Authoring and Versioning (WebDAV) is a set of extensions to HTTP, which allows user agents to collaboratively author contents directly in an HTTP web server by providing facilities for concurrency control and namespace operations, thus allowing the Web to be viewed as a writeable, collaborative medium, not just a read-only medium.	RFC 4918 ²
Standard	DOI	A digital object identifier (DOI) is a persistent identifier (aka PID or handle) used to uniquely identify an object, be it physical, digital, or abstract.	ISO 26324 ³

² <http://www.webdav.org/specs/rfc4918.html>

³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/81599.html>

9 Integration Options

Three different types of interoperability with the EOSC Data Transfer are possible, each representing a way to extend the capabilities of the EOSC Data Transfer API, as described below.

The EOSC Data Transfer REST API is a Java application. Owners or operators of data transfer services and data repositories integrate with the API by implementing one or more Java interfaces, extending the configuration file of the API, contributing their implementation to the code repository of the EOSC Data Transfer API. Redeployment of the API is needed to incorporate support for new data transfer services or new data repository parsers.

9.1 Integrating new DOI parsers

This integration extends the EOSC Data Transfer API's ability to parse different types of DOIs, which are pointing to data repositories that can be used, in whole or in part, as the source of data transfers. Those datasets that are hosted in data repositories that the EOSC Data Transfer service can parse will be available to transfer via the GUI of the service, which is integrated into the EOSC Portal and EOSC Marketplace.

9.2 Integrating new Data Transfer services

This integration allows EOSC users to transfer data (create and manage data transfers) via a new data transfer service, via new transfer protocols, to specific storage systems, or a combination of these.

9.3 Integrating new storage elements

This integration allows EOSC users to manage storage elements on target storage systems. Operations such as browse storage hierarchy, create/delete folders, rename/delete files are included.

10 Interoperability Guidelines

Please note that the Interoperability Guidelines are not intended to replace instruction manuals, help, or documentation. For details please refer to <https://github.com/EGI-Federation/eosc-data-transfer>.

This section describes the interoperability guidelines and provides the information required to enable each of the integration options listed in the previous section.

10.1 Prerequisites

In order to extend the capabilities of the EOSC Data Transfer service, the prerequisites below must be met.

Owners or operators of data repositories must:

- Be **able to determine if a DOI points to** a data record in **their repository**
- The repository **has a programmatic interface** that
 - **Can extract the URLs to the files** included in a data record
 - **Can use EOSC AAI access tokens**, for datasets that are not open for public access

Owners or operators of data transfer services must ensure that:

- The data transfer service **has a programmatic interface** that
 - **Can initiate a data transfer**, and optionally also
 - **Can manage data transfers** (query, stop)
 - **Can manage storage elements**
 - **Can use EOSC AAI access tokens**

10.2 Integration options

The following integration options are available:

1. integrating new DOI parsers,
2. integrating new data transfer services,
3. integrating new storage elements.

10.2.1 Integrating new DOI parsers

The API endpoint `GET /parser` that parses (the data repositories pointed to by) DOIs is extensible. To support parsing of a new type of data repository, all you have to do is implement the Java interface `ParserService` in a class of your choice, then register the Java class implementing the interface in the configuration of the API.

[Implement the Java interface for a generic DOI parser](#)

When the API endpoint `GET /parser` is called to parse a DOI, all configured parsers will be interrogated if they can parse the DOI, until one is identified that can. If no parser can handle the DOI, the call fails.

In order for the API to be able to use your new DOI parser, you have to add it to the configuration. This is where the API finds all available parsers to try when parsing of a DOI is requested.

[Add configuration for the new DOI parser](#)

10.2.2 Integrating new Data Transfer services

The API endpoints for creating and managing data transfers are extensible. To support creating and managing data transfers via a new data transfer service, and possibly management of storage elements in storage systems supported by the new data transfer service, all you have to do is implement the Java interface `TransferService` to wrap that specific data transfer service, then register your class implementing the interface as the handler for one or more destination storage types.

[Implement the interface for a generic data transfer service](#)

The methods can be split into two groups:

- The methods for handling data transfers **must** be implemented.
- The methods for storage elements **should** be implemented for storage types for which the method `canBrowseStorage()` returns `true`.

In order for the API to be able to use your new data transfer service, you have to add it to the configuration.

[Add configuration for the new data transfer service](#)

When a call is made to the API to create or manage a data transfer, or to manage storage elements, the API's implementation must decide which data transfer service to forward the request to. This decision is made based on the "storage type", which is a mandatory parameter to all endpoints dealing with data transfers and storage elements.

The **storage type** is just a designation of a subset of storage systems to be handled in a specific way (by a specific data transfer service). It is a pair of a **transfer protocol** and an (optional) **storage system instance** (hostname). Each wrapped data transfer service shall be configured to handle one or more storage types. This makes the API flexible, by allowing for not just an entire protocol (e.g. S3) to be handled by a specific transfer service, but also a more granular configuration where different destination storages that use the same protocol can be handled by different transfer services (the selection is made based on the hostname of the destination storage system).

[Register new destinations serviced by the new data transfer service](#)

10.2.3 Integrating new storage elements

The EOSC Data Transfer API supports managing storage elements in destination storage(s), provided the transfer service configured to handle those storage systems supports it. Each transfer service that gets integrated can optionally implement this functionality. Moreover, data transfer services that support multiple storage types can selectively implement this functionality for just a subset of the supported storage types.

To support this feature for a storage type, in your implementation of the Java interface `TransferService` (see [Section 10.2.2](#)), return `true` from the method `canBrowseStorage()`. The recommendation is to always implement this functionality (forward the calls to the configured transfer service) if the wrapped transfer service supports it, the method `canBrowseStorage()` is just a way to discover if the API can manage storage elements in a particular storage system. Clients can query if this functionality is implemented for a storage type by calling the endpoint `GET /storage/info`.

This functionality covers:

- listing the content of a storage element
- query information about a storage element
- rename a storage element (including its path, which means to move it)
- delete a storage element
- create a hierarchical storage element (folder/container/bucket)

Note that storage elements that store data (files/objects) can only be created by data transfers, not by the API endpoints in this group.

11 Privacy and Data Protection

All operations initiated by and all information retrieved by the EOSC Data Transfer API happen over an encrypted HTTPS connection. The API does not store any private information of its users, it merely forwards authentication headers to the transfer services it integrates and/or to the storage systems these transfer services interact with.

The EOSC Data Transfer API includes OpenTelemetry that collects traces, metrics, and logs of the operations initiated through the API. This is used strictly to track the health of the API and to diagnose problems. The telemetry architecture of the service is illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 - Telemetry of the EOSC Data Transfer API

12 Examples of solutions implementing the specifications

The initial release of the EOSC Data Transfer service integrates the EGI Data Transfer⁴ service, which is also available on the EOSC Marketplace. The EGI Data Transfer service is based on the FTS⁵ technology developed at CERN, and supports management of storage elements in storage systems with a WebDAV interface.

The EOSC Data Transfer service supports parsing DOIs, both in canonical DOI notation⁶ or as HTTP URLs, that point to data records in the following data repositories:

- Zenodo⁷
- B2SHARE⁸

⁴ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/egi-data-transfer>

⁵ <https://fts.web.cern.ch/fts>

⁶ https://www.doi.org/the-identifier/resources/handbook/2_numbering#2.6

⁷ <https://zenodo.org>

⁸ <https://www.eudat.eu/services/userdoc/b2share>

- European Synchrotron Radiation Facility⁹
- Any repository implementing Signposting¹⁰, of which the following link relations are supported
 - **item**
 - **linkset**
 - **identifier** (provided the PID points to a supported data repository)

⁹ <https://esrf.fr>

¹⁰ <https://signposting.org>